

Report on Design Principles for Emotion Sensitive Policy Making

Table of Contents

Executive summary.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. The emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing.....	5
3. Method.....	6
4. The threefold relationship between emotions and deliberative democratic innovations.....	9
5. Conclusion.....	13
5. Extended bibliography.....	14

Executive summary

PLEDGE brings theory and practice together and generates tools to promote effective policy-making and communication that will enhance emotionally intelligent and responsive democratic governance. This report lays the foundations for such a democratic design approach. To map the existing knowledge about deliberative democratic innovations and emotions, it combines an explanatory review of the literature with semi-structured interviews with international practitioners and experts in the field. In so doing, we establish and explore a new research agenda, with the potential to inform future initiatives that will enhance the link between citizens, policymakers and political elites through deliberative practices. We identified a threefold relationship that emotions have with deliberative democratic innovations: (i) emotions are *(dis)incentives* to participate and commit to deliberation; (ii) emotions are *features* of deliberative practices; and (iii) emotions are *outcomes* of deliberative practices. This report discusses these three dimensions with eyes fixed on the development of emotion-sensitive democratic innovations, and reflects on practices that further the emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing to occur.

1. Introduction

PLEDGE is a Horizon Europe funded project focusing on the emotional dynamics of political grievances and their implications for democratic politics. The PLEDGE project engages researchers, policymakers, and citizens in a collective effort to better understand citizens' emotions and develop practices and tools that promote emotionally responsive democratic governance and political communication, and foster pro-democratic forms of civic engagement.

PLEDGE adopts the Democratic Design approach to democracy, thinking about how to improve it, and how to design democratic innovations to that end. The central question a democratic designer asks is: 'How might, or how should, democratic institutions and practices be organized and activated for a given time and place?' (Saward, 2021). Democratic designers produce 'plans' or 'designs' that resemble, "a conception of a procedure for collective decision making comprising an arrangement of governing practices and devices enacting selected democratic principles, intended to meet or exceed the democratic minimum, driven by a democratic sensibility, reflexively according to context and purpose." (Saward 2021, 53).

The Democratic Design framework as formulated by Saward (i) is problem-driven: it identifies and creates democratic innovations and interventions in response to democratic problems or democratic incompleteness; (ii) is systemic in its approach (in contrast to 'single institution (re)design'); (iii) rejects the limiting, forced choice between existing models of democracy (participatory, deliberative, (post)representative etc.) in favour of a 'mix and match' approach where practices and devices based in various models can be sequenced and layered; (iv) stimulates ambition and creativity: democratic designers imagine what democracy can be and the ways in which it can be enacted, 'thinking the as-yet-unthought' (Saward 2021, 47); (v) is not merely academic, but constitutes 'theory for practice': democratic principles are 'thought together' with practices that enact those principles; (vi) is context specific: democratic designers design for a specific time and place. Regardless of any other democratic shortcomings designers need to address, the feminist take on democratic design insists that they begin from extant inequalities, and commit to make equality happen (Celis & Childs, 2023/forthcoming).

PLEDGE adopts approaches that produce emotion-sensitive democratic designs. Emotion-sensitive democratic designs depart from the idea that emotions are problematic and have no place in the processes and outcomes of policy and decision-making. In contrast, emotion-sensitive democratic designs fully acknowledge that: (i) emotions are intrinsic to all political actors and drive political behaviours, including the motivation to participate (and continue to participate) in democratic policy-making and decision-making processes; and they (ii) implement practices and processes to initiate, maintain or foster pro-democratic emotions and emotional mechanisms, and/or to limit, stop or reverse anti-democratic ones.

We begin by introducing the emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing (Salmela & von Scheve, 2018; Salmela & Szanto, forthcoming), which for PLEDGE is a key mechanism, and the way we proceeded to identify relevant gaps in the literature and current practice. The body of the paper discusses three types of relationship emotions occupy within deliberation and deliberative democratic innovation. First, we consider what we know about how these processes are shaped by emotions. Secondly, we explore which, and how, emotions can be (dis)incentives to participate and be(come) committed to deliberative processes. Thirdly, we discuss emotions as outcomes. Findings from the literature review, and the interviews, are jointly discussed (as the basis) for answering the question of what principles and practices are the most favourable in light of emotion-sensitive democratic innovations.

2. The emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing

In this contribution, we contribute to the development of democratic innovations able to deal with pro/anti-democratic grievances, and provide opportunities to build a democratic policymaking infrastructure that reflects greater sensitivity to emotions. While individual and shared emotions can partially bridge different values and identities in deliberative practices (Celis & Childs, 2020, 2023), insight into how and through which democratic innovations and interventions desirable emotional outcomes can be implemented remains embryonic. This work, thus provides a more robust theoretical foundation for design thinking and empirical testing of innovative solutions.

We begin from the premise that new democratic practices must be designed to support the *emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing* (EMSoS; Salmela & von Scheve, 2018; Britt & Heise, 2000; Gould, 2009). This mechanism involves two parallel transformations: (i) the self-identity as failure and inferior transforms into emancipated and optimistic without a change in its content, and (ii) the value of what was desired and unattainable individually is reinforced and transforms into a shared goal to be pursued in collective action with peer others. The concept is operationalized through the sharing of specific emotions (both triggers and outputs of the mechanism) or major concerns, and the lack of emotional repression. It is positively correlated with trust, efficacy, and internal locus of control, and negatively associated with resentment, reactionism, collective narcissism, conspiracy thinking and traits of victimhood. As put forward by the literature on 'affective practices' (Wetherell, 2012; von Scheve, 2012), EMSoS will likely be triggered in collective spheres where emotional reflexivity is present, and conducive to feeling rules for solidarity-oriented sharing initiated by empathetic and sympathetic emotional energy. This paper constitutes the first stage of collecting academic and field-based knowledge, from which experts and practitioners could reflect on when designing democratic innovations to trigger and harness this particular mechanism.

3. Method

Our ‘design-thinking’ work begins by compiling key insights on emotions and democratic innovations. Following Elstub and Escobar (2019) we define democratic innovations as “processes or institutions that are new to a policy issue, policy role, or level of governance, and developed to reimagine and deepen the role of citizens in governance processes by increasing opportunities for participation, deliberation and influence” (Elstub and Escobar 2019, p.11). Our state-of-the-art and desk research focuses on democratic innovations underpinned by a deliberative logic; because they foreground argumentative communication, in particular, the difficult interplay between feelings and reasoning (Maia & Hauber, 2020). More precisely, we decided to limit our literature study to what is known about emotions within what Elstub and Escobar (2019) define as the *mini-publics* and *collaborative governance* families of democratic innovations. Their architectural logics closely resemble each other, and both types of innovation have been mobilized in a multitude of policy areas, across all levels of governance and at all stages of the policy process. Elstub and Escobar (2019) suggest a typology of democratic innovations classifying them into four families based on their quasi-contingent (inclusion, participation, decision-making, influence) and contextual (policy area, policy stage, governance level) features (see Figure 1) - digital participation is not considered a family of its own. Democratic innovations such as referenda and citizen initiatives are built on plebiscite-based decision-making logic (von dem Berge & Poguntke, 2017) or vote-centric decision-making practices (Gherghina et al., 2020) that do not challenge the procedural and rationalizing logic underlying the current model of representative democracy. For its part, the participatory budgeting family relates to a narrower category, which although based on discursive and listening modes of participation, is still aggregative in reaching a final decision. Just like referenda and citizens initiatives, it leaves little room for deliberation, bargaining and negotiation. Moreover, the context in which participatory budgets are used is confined to local initiatives and public spending issues, whereas all the other families are easily adapted to other contexts.

Mini-publics and collaborative governance families rely on discursive expression and listening retaining deliberation at the core of their decision-making process. Their biggest difference, however, is how participants are selected. Whilst collaborative governance mainly relies on purposive selection, mini-publics use sortition in order to increase representativeness of participants’ and the outputs.

Democratic innovation family	Quasi-contingent features				Contextual features		
	Participant selection method	Mode of participation	Mode of decision-making	Extent of power and authority	Policy area	Level of governance	Stage of policy process
Mini-publics	Sortition	Discursive expression, voting and listening	Deliberation and aggregation	Variable: Personal benefits, advise and consult, communicative influence, co-governance and direct authority	Diverse (e.g. health, environment, social policy and constitutional reform)	Local, regional, national, and transnational	Various (agenda-setting, formulation and scrutiny)
Participatory budgeting	Self-selection, election and purposive selection	Voting, discursive expression and listening	Aggregation	Co-governance and direct authority	Public spending	Local	Formulation and decision-making
Referenda and citizen initiatives	Self-selection	Voting	Aggregation	Advise and consult and direct authority	Diverse	Local, regional and national	Decision-making
Collaborative governance	Self-selection, and purposive selection	Discursive expression and listening	Deliberation, and bargaining and negotiation	Variable: Personal benefits, advise and consult, communicative influence, co-governance and direct authority	Diverse	Local, regional, national and transnational	Multiple
Digital participation²	Self-selection, sortition, election and purposive selection	Discursive expression, voting, listening and observation	Deliberation, bargaining and negotiation, aggregation, no decision	Variable: Personal benefits, advise and consult, communicative influence, co-governance and direct authority	Diverse	Local, regional, national and transnational	Various (crowdsourcing, prioritising and scrutiny)

Figure 1. Families of democratic innovations (Elstub & Escobar, 2019, p. 25)

In both types, four categories of actor can be identified. First, the initiators of these processes are generally public authorities represented by their administration. They can also be experts pursuing scientific ends, individuals, or organized promoters wishing to take advantage of what these processes have to offer for a variety of purposes. Usually, they initiate deliberative processes to collect citizens’ opinions, get to know different perspectives in society, or elaborate technical recommendations in view of formulating and implementing new public policies (Bochmann & Hetze, 2022). Secondly, the organizers (and facilitators) of participatory deliberations are either the initiators themselves, or more traditionally, external organizations specialized in setting up – sometimes tailor-made – processes. Thirdly, the participants are predominantly citizens, sometimes joined by public representatives or policymakers in so-called ‘mixed’ deliberative processes. Practitioner 1 (see below) noted, however, that the term ‘stakeholders’ - either individual or collective - is probably more appropriate to take full account of the context in which those present operate, and the interests (and motivations) they defend. Fourthly, democratic innovations are generally observed by a series of external players such as academics or specialist organizations. These may not interact directly with the processes, but they nevertheless produce knowledge that can serve as the basis for creating new practices or refining existing ones. They may also sit

on scientific committees who monitor processes put in place by an organizing committee, in this case they may directly influence the process itself.

This contribution takes stock of the existing knowledge and practices developed by the latter two categories of actors. We are interested in knowledge and practices that link emotions with the specific deliberative democratic innovations we identify, not only to reveal blind spots, but also to draw lessons for the development of new practices geared to triggering EMSoS.

To further substantiate our understanding of current practices, their strengths and limitations, in accommodating emotions, we combined the literature review with 9 interviews with experts and practitioners (see Table 1). The interview guide (see Annex 2) was designed to explore specific research areas based on the gaps identified in the literature review. Identifying such gaps are the key to energizing new research areas, and informing future initiatives that enhance the link between citizens and policymakers. We asked experts and practitioners to reflect on what they know about the theory, and give insights on how emotions are regarded and processed in practice. The structure of the interview gave enough freedom for them to offer valuable information on aspects we might not have – as researchers – considered before.

Interviewees were informed the study had undergone ethical review from the Human Science Ethics Committee at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (reference ECHW_505-WP6). Interviews were conducted in French or English, recorded and transcribed. The quotes of interest have been translated into English for this report. The interviewees are referenced in the text generically so that, when a quotation comes from Expert 1, for example, the reference is E1 and Practitioner 1 is P1.

Label		Role	Date	Where
I1	E1	Expert	29 April 2024	Brussels
I2	P1	Practitioner	15 May 2024	Brussels
I3	E2	Expert	03 June 2024	Online
I4	P2	Practitioner	06 June 2024	Online
I5	E3	Expert	07 June 2024	Online
I6	P3	Practitioner	10 June 2024	Online
I7	P4	Practitioner	25 June 2024	Brussels
I8	E4	Expert	26 June 2024	Online
I9	P5	Practitioner	04 July 2024	Brussels

Table 1. List of interviews

We conducted an abductive thematic analysis of the content the interviews. This allowed us to account for the threefold relationship that emotions have with democratic innovations: (dis)incentives; features; and outcomes.

4. The threefold relationship between emotions and deliberative democratic innovations

From our reading of the literature and analysis of the interviews, three links between emotions and democratic innovations (DI) emerge: (1) emotions as (dis)incentives to participation in DI, (2) emotions as shaping innovative democratic processes, and (3) emotions as (parts of) the outcome of DI. The following sections discuss these three relationships in turn.

As mentioned above, our discussion includes findings from interviews with experts and practitioners, and from our literature research of emotions and deliberative democratic innovations. The latter is largely theoretical and/or normative, although a more empirically driven approach to the issue has recently become more prevalent. Most of this empirical scholarship adopts a ‘discrete-emotions approach’ (i.e. focusing on a small set of fundamental emotions that are universally shared among cultures and distinguishable by physiological, expressive and behavioural features) based either on (i) *Appraisal theories*, arguing that specific cognitive appraisal trends elicit discrete emotional reactions associated with specific coping mechanisms; (ii) *Affective Intelligence Theory*, arguing that emotional reactions are not formed on the basis of reason but precede it; or (iii) *Intergroup Emotions Theory*, arguing that individual-level and group-based discrete emotions have to be differentiated (Sirin & Villalobos, 2019; Vasilopoulos, 2019). The difficulty in providing a systemic study of ‘all the emotions’, is illustrated by the limited number of discrete emotions included in studies of democratic innovations. *Anger*, *aversion* and *anxiety* are, for example, ‘negative’ emotions that gain a lot of attention, while *enthusiasm*, *empathy* and *hope* are ‘positive’ emotions that are regularly investigated by deliberative democrats.

We summarize below the main lessons to be drawn from our investigation, highlighting the most salient points in relation to what is known about emotions in the context of DIs, and the design principles we should develop on this basis.

4.2.1 Emotions as (dis)incentives to participation in DIs

Although positive effects of emotions on participation seem to be very much related to mediating variables such as efficacy or political knowledge, which organisers of deliberative processes have little leverage (Bochmann & Hetze, 2022; Miscoiu & Gherghina, 2021; E1),

both the literature, the experts and practitioners highlighted that to make the best of emotions, deliberative formats need to be carefully designed. Emotions can increase participation and further commitment, but procedures have to be tailored to that end (Saam, 2018; Bächtiger et al., 2010; Mansbridge et al., 2006; Miscoiu & Gherghina, 2021; Bochmann & Hetze, 2022; P1, E3; Annex 1). *Enthusiasm, anxiety, hope*, and other emotions related to positive expectations about the process itself, can motivate participants to commit further to the tasks ahead (McClain, 2009; Stokkom, 2003). *Anger* can facilitate group solidarity and involvement (Palmer, 2024) but can also become destructive of the process if not handled carefully (Johnson et al., 2019).

Main findings:

A. Emotions recruit...

- Emotions are motivators to deliberate, disable habits and recruit reason (e.g. Marcus, 2002; Neblo, 2020; Practitioner 2)
- ! Socio-economic background, efficacy or political knowledge are moderators of the incentive power of emotions (e.g. Expert 1, Miscoiu & Gherghina, 2021; Bochmann & Hetze, 2022)
 - Building knowledge and efficacy before deliberation
 - Adapting the technicality of the content of the discussion
 - Using emotional cues or appeals to recruit participants

B. ... but also have to be recruited

- Emotions generated by the procedures can also promote exit (e.g. Jacquet, 2017; McClain, 2009; Saam, 2018)
 - ➔ ! Active listening on the part of moderators and DIs initiators (e.g. Dembinska & Montambeault, 2015; Pitts et al., 2017; Stains & Sarrouf, 2022; Practitioners 1, 2, 3 and 5)
- Emotions increase commitment beyond participation, but procedures have to be tailored for that (e.g. Bächtiger et al., 2010; Leino & Kulha, 2023; Mansbridge et al., 2006)

- ➔ Varying emotionally intense sequences (sharing personal stories, face-to-face debates, future thinking, etc.) with moments for introspection (e.g. Johnson et al., 2019)

4.2.2 Emotions as shaping innovative democratic processes

The first type of relationship focuses on emotions as (dis)incentives to deliberate. Here, we consider how increased thought is being given to how emotions are felt/used by participants and facilitators, and how nature of deliberation is enabled, shaped, and ensured to go in the right direction. Such knowledge was built on the increasing, yet still limited, capacity of experts and practitioners to measure shifting emotional states during deliberations. Positive emotions like *happiness* or *hopefulness* put participants in the right frame of mind for creative exchange, whilst negative emotions like *anger*, can drive group identities that are detrimental to debate. Emotions also serve as the signals, or means, by which participants or facilitators can prioritize certain points of discussion over others. Emotions are thus important inputs to deliberative democracy.

Procedures do, however, need to be flexible and creative in order to moderate emotions. Indeed, our overview suggests that structured, albeit tailor-made for context, forms of dialogue that are geared towards listening, acknowledging and taking the emotional reasoning of the participants into account, have greater responsiveness to grievances. The use of games can also facilitate discussion while increasing emotions like joy or empathy. In this sense, the goal is to avoid the development of group identities based on emotions that are likely to be detrimental to deliberation.

Main findings:

A. Emotions are meaningful inputs...

- Enabling tools helping participants to navigate deliberations (Neblo, 2020):
 - Help transforming emotional evaluations of a given reality into explicit propositional form
 - Help considering and prioritizing competing factual claims
- ➔ Competitive-collaborative procedures (with game mechanics?) can make useful emotions to emerge (e.g. Johnson et al., 2016, 2019; Gastil, 2022; Gordon et al., 2016, 2017, Practitioner 1, Expert 3)

B. ... but only when procedures are flexibly structured

- Detrimental emotions and resulting attitudes (e.g. group polarization) emerge when lack of facilitation, clear procedural rules reflecting deliberative norms and balanced informational materials (e.g. Richards et al., 2022; Stains and Sarrouf, 2022; Thompson and Hoggett, 2001; Expert 4)
 - ➔ Mutual understanding and connection can be improved by planning dialogues, fostering facilitators' connection to participants and transparent and predictable formats (e.g. Bächtiger, 2010; Stains and Sarrouf, 2022)

4.2.3 Emotions as (part of) DI outcomes

The third relationship between emotions and DI concerns emotion as (parts of) the DI outcomes. The literature about emotions and democratic innovations is quite developed on this dimension. Overall, emotions *as* (parts of the) outcome of democratic innovation relate to two different dimensions. First, the procedural outcome of the process itself (e.g. the recommendations) – and debates around its formulation – can elicit emotional responses that will shape participants' perception of the outcome itself. In this sense, emotions are generally seen as ends in themselves, or as instrumental in the pursuit of other, longer-term, objectives like increasing participants' preparedness to accept difficult political decisions, or building loyalty to deliberative practices (see below).

Secondly, the publicization or implementation of the procedural outcome of the deliberative process can also provoke emotional appraisal by the wider audience. The outcome, when publicised to a wider audience, will inevitably be perceived through people's emotional prisms. Experts and practitioners tell us that capturing the emotional content of the debates that preceded its production is undoubtedly a major challenge to meet if emotional individuals, both internal and external to the process, are to be brought into dialogue. Without this, there is a risk of presenting an external audience, carrying its own 'bag of emotions' (P2), with a technical output devoid of an emotional anchor that public opinion could use to position itself in relation to it.

Main findings:

A. Democratic innovations' outcomes elicit emotional responses from the participants...

- Emotional responses to the exercise increase acceptance of contentious political decisions, sense of agency, efficacy, loyalty to deliberative practices, etc. (e.g. Andrews, 2022; Leino & Kulha, 2023; Practitioner 3)
- ! Emotions at the start of the process can create high expectations which need to be met (e.g. Stains and Sarrouf, 2022; Practitioner 3)
 - ➔ Design to “equalize” or take stock of initial emotions? (Expert 1; Practitioner 5)
 - ➔ Emotions as end-goals (Practitioners 3 and 5; Expert 4)

B. ... but also from the wider audience

- Dis' outcomes can influence public opinion and bridge the gap between opposing camps (e.g. Suiter et al., 2020)
- If matching public opinion's emotional state, the outcome can increase support and implementation success (Practitioner 2, Experts 1 and 3)
 - ➔ Politicians and policy makers have to understand the emotional context of the processes they initiate (Miscoiu & Gherghina, 2021, Practitioner 1)
 - ➔ The emotional content of the process has to be publicized as well

5. Conclusion

Emotions are undeniably central to the policymaking process. With this assertion, the PLEDGE project builds on and advances a growing body of research that reaffirms the significance of emotions across various domains, including politics, political theory, communication, psychology, cognitive science, representative democracy, and democratic innovation (Bakker et al., 2021; Capelos et al., 2022; Celis et al., 2021; Close and van Haute, 2020; Demertzis, 2020; Jacobs et al., 2024; Johnson et al., 2016, 2019; Knops, 2023; Maia & Hauber, 2020; Marcus, 2000). Despite this momentum, this emotional turn still faces

opposition—particularly from proponents of the dominant model underpinning contemporary representative institutions, which continues to rest on an ideal of purely rational, procedural deliberation as the foundation for legitimate decision-making. This tension invites a fundamental question: how can emotion be reintegrated into policymaking, especially as citizens' emotional experiences and grievances increasingly shape their political attitudes and behaviours?

This paper marks an initial step toward fulfilling one of PLEDGE's key aims: to explore, refine, and empirically evaluate novel approaches that embrace the value of emotionality within democratic policymaking. To this end, PLEDGE adopts an emotion-sensitive democratic design approach. Our work began by mapping existing knowledge at the intersection of democratic innovations and emotions, identifying where and how these domains converge, and extracting key lessons to inform the development of emotionally attuned democratic practices. We focused specifically on deliberative democratic innovations, as these are the only political processes that actively cultivate argumentative communication—where the interplay between emotion and reasoning is most evident (Maia & Hauber, 2020).

Beyond this comprehensive literature review, we conducted interviews with nine practitioners and experts in democratic innovation. From our analysis, we identified three key ways in which emotions intersect with deliberative democratic innovations, reflecting both scholarly perspectives and insights from our interviews: (1) emotions as (dis)incentives for participation in deliberative innovations (DIs); (2) emotions as influential in shaping the process of democratic innovation itself; and (3) emotions as part of the outcomes generated by DIs. One central finding is that, although the empirical literature exploring the role of emotion in deliberative settings is quite advanced, many practitioners still view emotion—especially intense or negative expressions—as disruptive to successful deliberation. Emotional outbursts are often interpreted as signs of deliberative failure.

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